

Short pulse laser induced thermo-elastic deformation imaging

TIANSI WANG,^{1,*} TOM PFEIFFER,² MIN WU,¹ WOLFGANG WIESER,³ WOLFGANG DRAXINGER,²
ANTONIUS F.W. VAN DER STEEN,^{1,4,5} ROBERT HUBER² AND GIJS VAN SOEST¹

¹Thorax Center, Erasmus University Medical Center, P. O. Box 2040, Rotterdam 3000 CA, The Netherlands

²Institut für Biomedizinische Optik, Universität zu Lübeck, Peter-Monnik-Weg 4, 23562 Lübeck Germany

³Lehrstuhl für Biomolekulare Optik, Fakultät für Physik, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München, Oettingenstr.
67, München 80538, Germany

⁴Shenzhen Institutes of Advanced Technology, Chinese Academy of Sciences, 518055 Shenzhen, China

⁵Department of Imaging science and Technology, Delft University of Technology, Postbus 5, Delft 2600 AA, The
Netherlands

*Corresponding author: tswang1983@gmail.com

Absorption of nanosecond laser pulses induces rapid thermo-elastic deformation in tissue, i.e. a sub-micrometer scale displacement happens within a couple of microseconds. In this study, we initially investigate the depth-resolved deformation using a 1.5 MHz phase-sensitive optical coherence tomography (OCT) system. Functional images can be reconstructed based on the detected deformation, which enables a new imaging modality called thermo-elastic deformation imaging (TDI). Our results show that the associated displacement is related to the optical absorption of the short laser pulses. The TDI images can provide tissue type information in addition to the conventional OCT images.

Phase-sensitive optical coherence tomography (phase-sensitive OCT), a subtype of OCT, can detect tissue motion on nanometer-to-micrometer length scales using the phase signal of OCT. Depending on the nature of the excitation, different functional images can be reconstructed, i.e. mechanical stimulus yields elastic-deformation images (optical coherence elastography) [1-4], and continuous-wave laser illumination yields photo-thermal deformation images (photo-thermal OCT). The excitations sources are typically with large physical dimension and require relatively long accumulation time (>millisecond). In this letter, we will use nanosecond laser pulses to induce rapid thermo-elastic deformation in tissue, which can be detected by phase-sensitive OCT within a couple of microseconds.

Previous studies find that short pulse laser causes thermo-elastic deformation in tissue [5-8]. The absorbed energy first leads to a non-uniform temperature rise in the sample, which causes a rapid thermo-elastic expansion with an elastic wave propagated. A quasi-steady-state regime is reached when the sample reaches equilibrium and the net force of the sample is zero. A relaxation phase is then reached when the stress slowly decay to zero because temperature of the sample becomes uniform due to the heat dissipation. In a linear and isotropic material, the one dimensional displacement $u(z, t)$ in the quasi-steady state follows,

$$u(z, t) = u_0 \left\{ \exp \left[-\mu_{att} c_L \left(t - \frac{z}{c_L} \right) \right] + \exp \left[-\mu_{att} c_L \left(t + \frac{z}{c_L} \right) \right] - 2 \exp \left(-\mu_{att} z \right) \right\}, \quad (1)$$

$$u_0 = \frac{\mu_a (1+\nu) \beta P}{\mu_{att} (1-\nu) C 3\rho} \quad (2)$$

where β is the thermal expansion coefficient, K is the bulk modulus, ρ is the density, c_L is the sound speed μ_a is the absorption coefficient, μ_{att} is the attenuation coefficient ν is the Poisson's ratio, C is the heat capacity and P is the power density of the laser pulse [6]. In this Letter, we use superfast phase-sensitive OCT to investigate the thermo-elastic deformation focusing on optical absorption. We further introduce a new imaging method called thermo-elastic deformation imaging (TDI).

The TDI prototype consists of a wavelength-tunable pulse laser and a phase-sensitive OCT system. The tunable laser (OPOTEK Vibrant B/355-II) has pulse duration of 5 ns and a repetition rate of 10 Hz. The laser was operated at 500 nm wavelengths with a power of 2 mJ per pulse. The excitation laser beam was coupled into a multimode fiber with a 400 μ m core diameter. The phase-sensitive OCT system is based on a 1.5 MHz Fourier Domain Mode Locked (FDML) laser [9-11] with a central wavelength of 1310 nm, a swept range of 90 nm, an output power of 20 mW, a sensitivity of 102 dB, an image depth of 4.0 mm in air and a phase stability of 0.5 nm in air. A custom-made ball lens probe focuses the OCT beam at 2 mm distance forming a 20 μ m beam waist. The ball lens probe and the multimode fiber were integrated into a forward-looking probe with an angle of 30 degrees. The schematic program of the TDI prototype is shown in Fig. 1a.

Fig. 1. (a) Schematic program of TDI prototype. (b) M-mode OCT image of phantom. (c) Phase-resolved image of phantom showing the thermo-elastic deformation. FDML: Fourier Domain Mode Locked; PC: polarization controller; BPD: balanced photo detector; DAQ: data acquisition card; Arrows indicate the laser pulse irradiation.

For each laser pulse, successful and co-located A-lines were acquired and processed generating M-mode images. The phase-shift was extracted by subtracting the phase data before and after the laser pulse irradiation. The phase-shift ϕ was converted to displacement d following

$$d = \phi \frac{\lambda_0}{4\pi n}, \quad (2)$$

, where n is the refractive index of the sample and λ_0 is the central wavelength of the OCT laser source. The maximum depth-resolved deformation was generated by taking the mean values of 4 neighboring processed A-lines that were acquired right after the deformation accumulation (1.3 microseconds after the irradiation). 2D TDI image can further be created by moving the forward-looking probe linearly at a speed of 0.2 mm/s.

Fig. 1 (b) and (c) shows the detection of the thermo-elastic deformation in a polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) phantom mixed with 2% red ink. First 2D TDI image consisting of 170 deformation-related A-lines was acquired in a PVA phantom with red ink dye injected at a depth of 200 μm beneath the surface. There is no trace of the colored part can be observed in the conventional OCT image (Fig. 2a). However, the TDI image clearly shows the location and shape of the colored part with a promising contrast due to the strong deformation that is related to the optical absorption. It can also be seen that the associated displacement is in both upwards and downwards directions. An upward (positive) displacement on the surface can also be observed which is due to the “pushing” of the colored part.

Fig. 2. TDI-OCT images of 3-cycle PVA phantom with red ink dye injected at a depth of 200 μm . (a) Structural OCT image; (b) phase-resolved TDI image showing the detected displacement. Scale bar: 1.0 mm; upwards is positive.

In summary, we demonstrate the study of short laser pulse induced thermo-elastic detection using a super fast OCT engine. Our phantom studies show that the associated displacement can be detected within a couple microseconds. The deformation relies upon the absorption of the laser pulse. Functional TDI images can be reconstructed based on the displacement providing tissue/phantom type information in addition to the conventional OCT images.

1. T. Ma, W. J. Qi, R. Li, Q. F. Zhou, K. K. Shung, and Z. P. Chen, "Optoacoustic Elastography for Tissue Biomechanical Property Characterization Using a Ring Transducer," *Ieee Int Ultra Sym*, 1154-1157 (2013).

2. B. F. Kennedy, S. H. Koh, R. A. McLaughlin, K. M. Kennedy, P. R. T. Munro, and D. D. Sampson, "Strain estimation in phase-sensitive optical coherence elastography," *Biomedical optics express* **3**, 1865-1879 (2012).
3. M. Singh, C. Wu, C. H. Liu, J. S. Li, A. Schill, A. Nair, and K. V. Larin, "Phase-sensitive optical coherence elastography at 1.5 million A-Lines per second," *Optics letters* **40**, 2588-2591 (2015).
4. B. F. Kennedy, K. M. Kennedy, and D. D. Sampson, "A Review of Optical Coherence Elastography: Fundamentals, Techniques and Prospects," *Ieee J Sel Top Quant* **20** (2014).
5. B. Soroushian, W. M. Whelan, and M. C. Kolios, "Study of laser-induced thermoelastic deformation of native and coagulated ex-vivo bovine liver tissues for estimating their optical and thermomechanical properties," *Journal of biomedical optics* **15** (2010).
6. B. P. Payne, V. Venugopalan, B. B. Mikic, and N. S. Nishioka, "Optoacoustic determination of optical attenuation depth using interferometric detection," *Journal of biomedical optics* **8**, 264-272 (2003).
7. I. Itzkan, D. Albagli, M. L. Dark, L. T. Perelman, C. Vonrosenberg, and M. S. Feld, "The Thermoelastic Basis of Short Pulsed-Laser Ablation of Biological Tissue," *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* **92**, 1960-1964 (1995).
8. S. R. Aglyamov, S. Wang, S. Y. Emelianov, and K. V. Larin, "A three dimensional solution for laser-induced thermoelastic deformation of the layered medium," *Optical Elastography and Tissue Biomechanics Iii* **9710** (2016).
9. R. Huber, D. C. Adler, and J. G. Fujimoto, "Buffered Fourier domain mode locking: Unidirectional swept laser sources for optical coherence tomography imaging at 370,000 lines/s," *Optics letters* **31**, 2975-2977 (2006).
10. D. C. Adler, W. Wieser, F. Trepanier, J. M. Schmitt, and R. A. Huber, "Extended coherence length Fourier domain mode locked lasers at 1310 nm," *Optics express* **19**, 20930-20939 (2011).
11. W. Wieser, T. Klein, W. Draxinger, and R. Huber, "Fully automated 1.5 MHz FDML laser with more than 100mW output power at 1310 nm," **9541**, 954116 (2015).